

Assessment Of Serum ALT Levels In Chronic Hepatitis C Patients In Accordance With Gender

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Abstract

Introduction: Hepatitis C virus is an RNA virus that is affecting almost 170 million people worldwide. Hepatitis C is also associated with increased incidence of chronic liver diseases, liver cirrhosis and hepatocellular carcinoma. Therefore serum levels of ALT are considered to be the more specific indicator of hepatocellular damage than serum levels of AST. Serum ALT levels vary according to age and gender.

Materials And Methods: This is a descriptive cross sectional study that was conducted from September 2016 to April 2017 at Centre of Liver Diseases of Holy Family Hospital, Rawalpindi after approval from Institutional Research Forum of Rawalpindi Medical University. Consecutive non-probability sampling technique was used.

The findings of serum ALT levels were classified into 5 groups: <40u/l, 41-60u/l, 61-80u/l, 81-100u/l and >100u/l. Normal value of serum ALT levels was <40u/l.

Patients were divided into 5 age groups: 10-25 years, 25-40 years, 40-55 years, 55-70 years and >70 years.

The data was analyzed using SPSS v22. Frequency and Percentages were calculated for gender, age and serum ALT levels.

Results: 405 (198 male and 207 female) patients were included in this research. Mean ALT levels in male patients were 89.5u/l while in female patients were 70.4u/l. The difference between their mean values was significant (P=0.016). Serum ALT levels of 24.2% (98) patients were within normal range (<40u/l) while they were deranged (>40u/l) in 75.8% (307) patients. Serum ALT levels were higher in female patients in all age groups

Conclusion: It was concluded that serum ALT levels vary significantly with age and gender. Elevation of serum ALT is seen more frequently in male than in female patients although mean ALT

levels are higher in female patients in all age groups than in male patients.

Introduction

Liver plays an important role in the metabolism of carbohydrates, lipids and proteins. It also detoxifies waste products of metabolism by various processes like amino acid deamination. It is responsible for synthesis and secretion of bile. It also synthesizes lipoproteins, plasma proteins and clotting factors.¹ It also synthesizes many enzymes that catalyze various biochemical reactions of the body like Alanine Transaminase (ALT), Aspartate Transaminase (AST), Gamma Glutamyl Transferase (GGT), Lactate Dehydrogenase (LDH) etc.² Hepatitis C virus is an RNA virus that is affecting almost 170 million people worldwide.² It has 6 different genotypes. Genotype 3a is the most prevalent genotype of HCV in Pakistan.^{3, 4} Hepatitis C is also associated with increased incidence of chronic liver diseases, liver cirrhosis and hepatocellular carcinoma.^{5, 6} It has been established that serum levels of ALT and AST are deranged in chronic liver diseases like hepatitis. ALT is 3000 times while AST is 7000 times more active in liver than in serum. ALT is exclusively cytoplasmic while AST is present in both mitochondria as well as cytoplasm. The half-life of ALT is 47±10 hours.⁷⁻⁹ ALT and AST are synthesized throughout the body. AST is found primarily in skeletal muscles, heart, liver and kidney while ALT is found primarily in liver and kidney. It is present in lesser amounts in skeletal muscles and heart.¹⁰⁻¹² Activity of ALT is higher than the activity of AST in chronic liver diseases except for Alcoholic Hepatitis and Reye Syndrome. That is because most of the liver diseases decrease hepatocyte activity of both mitochondrial as well as cytoplasmic AST, but alcohol decreases cytoplasmic activity of AST only and induces release of AST from mitochondria.¹³⁻¹⁶ Therefore serum levels of ALT are considered to be the

more specific indicator of hepatocellular damage than serum levels of AST.¹⁷ Serum ALT levels vary according to age and sex.¹⁷⁻¹⁸ Considering the significance of serum ALT levels and variation with gender, the objective of this study was to compare the mean serum levels of ALT in patients of hepatitis C in accordance with gender.

Materials & Methods

This is a descriptive cross sectional study that was conducted from September 2016 to April 2017 at Centre of Liver Diseases of Holy Family Hospital, Rawalpindi after approval from Institutional Research Forum of Rawalpindi Medical University. Consecutive non-probability sampling technique was used.

From the patients presenting to Centre of Liver Diseases during the period of 8 months, 405 patients with diagnosis of Hepatitis C confirmed by ELISA were included in this study. Patients receiving hepatotoxic drugs, less than 10 or more than 80 years of age, with metabolic liver diseases, with acute hepatitis (hepatitis A and E) or patients with hepatitis B or D were excluded.

Serum ALT levels were performed within 24 hours of the diagnosis of Hepatitis C by drawing 5ml blood from antecubital vein under strict aseptic conditions. Using Rotofix-32 machine, Blood was centrifuged for 3-5 minutes while Beckman Coulter AU-480 automation machine was used to determine serum ALT levels

The findings of serum ALT levels were classified into 5 groups: <40u/l, 41-60u/l, 61-80u/l,81-100u/l and >100u/l. Normal value of serum ALT levels was <40u/l.

Patients were divided into 5 age groups: 10-25 years, 25-40 years, 40-55 years, 55-70 years and >70 years.

The data was analyzed using SPSS v22. Frequency and Percentages were calculated for gender, age, genotype of virus and serum ALT levels. Kolmogorov Smirnov & Shapiro Wilk tests were applied to check normality of distribution of data for serum ALT levels-Gender and Serum ALT-Various age groups. Independent Student's "t" test was applied to compare mean serum ALT levels of male with female patients.

Results

405 (198 male and 207 female) patients were included in this research. Mean ALT levels in male patients were 89.485u/l while in female patients were 70.974u/l. The difference between their mean values was statistically significant. (P=0.016) (P<0.05) (Table I) (Graph I)

TABLE I: This table provides mean serum ALT levels in male and female Hepatitis C Patients

GENDER	MEAN SERUM ALT LEVELS	Independent students "t" test
MALE	89.48	t=2.430, df= 403, P=0.016
FEMALE	70.37	

(Table II): Gender wise distribution of patients and their serum ALT levels have been classified into various ranges

Serum ALT Levels Range	Frequency	%age	GENDER			
			MALE		FEMALE	
			Frequency	%age	Frequency	%AGE
<40 u/l	98	24.2 %	41	20.7 %	57	27.5 %
41-60 u/l	90	22.2 %	36	18.2 %	54	26.1 %
61-80 u/l	72	17.8 %	40	20.2 %	32	15.5 %
81-100 u/l	57	14.1 %	25	12.6 %	32	15.5 %
>100 u/l	88	21.7 %	41	28.3 %	32	15.5 %

(Table III): Age wise distribution of patients and their mean serum ALT levels

AGE GROUPS	NO. OF PATIENTS	%OF PATIENTS	MEAN SERUM ALT LEVELS
10-25	24	5.9 %	110.21
26-40	99	24.4 %	87.54
41-55	199	49.1 %	75.53
56-70	81	20.0 %	72.30
>70	2	0.5 %	44.50
TOTAL	405	100 %	

The tables explains the relation between mean serum ALT levels and various age groups of the patients. The frequency of patients has also been stated

(GRAPH I): Relation between Gender-Age and Mean serum ALT levels.

This graph explains that mean levels of serum ALT are higher in all age groups in female patients as compared to male patients.

Serum ALT levels of 24.2% (98) patients were within normal range (<40u/l) while they were deranged (>40u/l) in 75.8% (307) patients.

It was observed that Serum ALT levels of most of the female (27.5%) patients lied within normal range (<40u/l) while they were severely deranged (>100u/l) in most of the male (28.3%) patients. (Table II)

The data was normally distributed according to Kolmogorov Smirnov & Shapiro Wilk tests.

The mean age of the patients was 46.46 years, 45.63years in male while 47.25years in female patients. Patients were also classified according to their age groups. 49.1% (199) patients belonged to age group of 41-55 years. The maximum values of serum ALT levels were observed in young patients 10-25 years age. (Table III)

Serum ALT levels were higher in female patients in all age groups. (Graph I)

Discussion

Elevation in serum levels of aminotransferases is considered to be an indicator of hepatocellular damage owing to their hepatic concentration. However ALT is considered to be more specific for liver damage than AST.¹⁹ Serum ALT levels increase significantly with periportal bridging necrosis. It has been noted that there is a linear relationship between the degree of elevation of serum ALT and extent of liver injury as predicted by HAI score.²⁰

Growing evidence has suggested that up to 25% of patients with chronic hepatitis C virus infection have persistently normal aminotransferase levels (10% to 40%, according to different studies).²¹ It is also in accordance with our study in which serum ALT levels of 24.2% of the patients were within normal range.²²⁻²⁴

Elevation of serum ALT levels in PCR_RNA positive HCV patients with normal controls has been documented in 85% of the patients.²⁵ The linear regression model developed a relationship between RT-PCR tested for HCV RNA viral load and serum ALT levels⁽²⁶⁾ The relation of liver enzymes with viral load has also been developed. It was observed that levels of ALT and other hepatic enzymes had significant association with the stage of liver fibrosis and the grade of inflammation.²⁷ It has been concluded by previously done studies that both ALT and AST can be the useful markers for Chronic Hepatitis C. However, the AST might elevate alone, which suggests

that measuring AST may be useful only when the ALT is consistently normal. AST/ALT ratio ≥ 1 is highly suggestive of liver cirrhosis.²⁸ The relation between duration of HCV infection and elevation of ALT levels has also been established.²⁹

In a study conducted in Peshawar, it was observed that Majority of the patients of chronic hepatitis were female, in age group 21-40 years, and having ALT in range of 41-80 U/L.³⁰ These observations are in accordance with our study as 40% patients had serum ALT levels in the range 41-80 U/L and 74% patients belonged to age group 26-55 years which is also in accordance with the study of Farooqi et al.

Testing for HCV antibodies and hepatitis B surface antigens is advisable for all patients presenting with a mild increase in aminotransferase levels and at high risk of developing hepatitis.³¹⁻³⁴ It has been stated that in patients with an ALT level between 50-100 IU/l, HCV prevalence is tenfold the prevalence in general population, whereas HBV prevalence is not affected. Therefore, diagnostic follow-up for HCV is suggested in these patients.²¹

Ruhl et al conducted a study to determine upper limits of normal levels of ALT in the population of United States. It was observed that for HCV RNA positive men, median ALT was 53 while for women it was 36 as compared to 75 and 57 respectively in our study. Since study conducted by Ruhl et al is a survey conducted for screening purposes and targeted general population, therefore the values are comparatively lower as compared to this study.³⁵

It has been stated by some studies that the degree of aminotransferase alteration is a poor guide to the severity of the disease in patients with established chronic viral hepatitis. However in cases with an AST/ALT ratio greater than 1, there is significant chance of progression to liver cirrhosis. An AST/ALT ratio greater than 1 can be found in 4% of patients with chronic hepatitis C infection and in 79% of patients who also have liver cirrhosis.³⁶

Puoti et al concluded that patients with HCV RNA positive patients with normal ALT levels were more likely to be female which is in accordance with our study since it was observed that 58% of the HCV RNA positive patients with normal ALT levels were female.³⁷

Conclusion

It was concluded that serum ALT levels vary significantly with gender as mean serum ALT levels in female are higher than mean serum ALT levels of male.

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